

Welcome to the fourth edition of the ENTRUST newsletter! May was an eventful month for the ENTRUST project. The team kicked off the month by participating in two industry events and wrapped it up with the 3rd plenary meeting in Lisbon, Portugal. Discover more about these activities and get the latest updates about the project in this edition of our newsletter.

Tackling the lack of cybersecurity implementations in CMDs

As the ENTRUST project progresses, we wanted to remind you of its use cases. The project's framework will be evaluated in four real-world use cases ranging from wearable and medical devices used for remote patient monitoring to high-end stationary equipment used in hospitals and clinics.

[Learn more](#)

Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting

Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data

Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Well-being of Patients and Carers

Ambient Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living

ENTRUST 3rd Plenary Meeting in Lisbon

On May 14th-15th, the EnTrust Project consortium gathered for the **3rd Plenary Meeting** in Lisbon, Portugal. On the first day, the focus was on a technical overview session while the second day was dedicated to discussing the current implementation status of various project aspects.

[Learn more](#)

Latest from our blog

Physical Unclonable Functions for Protecting the Operation of Connected Medical Devices

The healthcare sector is undergoing a profound transformation with the integration of CMDs. However, the widespread adoption of CMDs also raises significant concerns regarding data security and patient privacy.

[Learn more](#)

Data security in remote patient monitoring

In this article, **Arnor Solberg** and **Erik Hogue Mathisen** from **Tellu** provide their expertise on the importance of security and privacy in Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM) solutions.

[Learn more](#)

Events

WEBINAR
10 MAY 2024
10 AM - 11:30 AM CEST

Webinar: Elevating Healthcare Security

[Learn more](#)

ENTRUST at the BEYOND Exposition

[Learn more](#)

Partners

